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SAFETY PRECAUTION FOR THE ELECTRIC THREE WHEELS IN SRI LANKA

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ABSTRACT

Electric vehicles offer a number of advantages over the conventional combustion engines. Lower local emission and higher energy efficiency are the most important factors found in electric vehicles. Sri Lanka is not very familiar with electric vehicles, especially electrical three-wheels. Most of the electric three-wheels are manufactured without safety precautions, and the major disadvantage of the three-wheels is passengers' safety. Due to the safety issues, Sri Lankan **Registry of Motor Vehicles (RMV)** will not allow vehicle importers to sell their electric vehicles. Due to this problem, companies are looking for safety devices which can be used with electric vehicles (three-wheels). The aim of this project is to develop an electrical safety system for the passenger's safety.

When the abnormality is detected from the safety unit the entire electrical system of the vehicle will shut down immediately. The electric system of the vehicles comprises three-phase motor and high current consuming devices such as inverters. The main power supply was 72 VDC and the safety unit was designed to detect current variation 60 – 380 A. **High Current Switching Controller (HCSC)** was the main power controller of the safety system and the **IGBT** unit was controlled by the **ATMEL** microcontroller. Industrial current sensors are used to detect abnormalities of the electrical system of the vehicle.

According to the test results, the switching system was in response to the vehicle's safety issues such as current leakage within 10 – 40 ms of time. After abnormality detection the entire electrical system was shut down immediately.

Keywords: Safety Precaution, Electrical Safety, Three-Phase motors, IGBT, ATMEL, Microcontroller, Inverter